

WORK VALUES INVENTORY OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS OF MALUNGON DISTRICTS: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Abstract: The study aimed to determine the work values of junior high school teachers of Malungon Districts and provided necessary intervention program based on the least common work values. Cross sectional research design was utilized to gather responses from the respondents. The respondents of the study were the 187 Junior High School Teachers of the four districts of Malungon. They were chosen through a simple random technique by means of draw lots. The researcher used the Work Values Inventory developed by Donald Super. Quantitative data processing and appropriate statistical tools were used to come up at specific computation, analysis, and interpretations of results. The findings of the study were validated and interpreted by a psychometrician. Data revealed that there was one least common work values among Junior High School Teachers of East, South and West Malungon Districts which was Management. While, Aesthetic was found to be the least common work values among Junior High School Teachers of North Malungon. Based on the results of the study, the researcher proposed an intervention program.

Keywords: educational management, work values, junior high school teachers, intervention, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Work values play a critical influence on an employee's performance in any workplace. Similarly, in education, a teacher's success in their activity can be ascribed to work values. Teaching necessitates working with a variety of people who exhibit a variety of behaviors. It is not easy to be surrounded by pressure to succeed in one's chosen work; it is up to the teacher to deal with the stress that comes with their job. Therefore, determining and understanding the work values of teachers necessitate considerable effort. Teachers' work values influence their behavior, particularly during the working process.

Their values influence what they do in their work to a large extent (Prabjandee, 2020; Rajendran, Watt & Richardson, 2020; Tran, 2020).

With this, Junior High School teachers must understand their work values to do their jobs well. Work values are a factor in determining teachers' work performance. Teachers with positive work values are more likely to carry out their duties and responsibilities as teachers despite the pressures and stress of their profession. Furthermore, attitudes/values are a strong predictor of effective teaching performance. Teachers who have a positive attitude contribute more competently to the process of child education. Moreover, a positive work value every teacher possesses and demonstrates is vital to the success of the learners, the school, the community, and the department (Ali & Panatik, 2018; Blazar & Kraft, 2017; Evangelista, 2019).

Evidently, the work values of Junior High School teachers in the four districts of Malungon are put to the test, especially for those who are not only required to solely teach but to do other critical related work, which can hamper their performance as a teacher. Aside from the time-consuming classroom preparations such as lesson planning, making of instructional materials, classroom structuring, and the responsibility of handling a diverse range of learners, teachers are also required to participate in different local activities and other extracurricular activities (Epstein, 2018; Giray, 2021; Woofter, 2019).

Due to a lack of research on work values, teachers do not know how to deal with the stress and pressures they face at work, leading to poor work values. Nevertheless, newspapers and televisions thrive with news of teachers assaulting physically and mentally harming the students. Teachers who abuse learners show they are not successful in achieving the tasks assigned to them (Arieli, Sagiv & Roccas, 2020; Briggs & Hawkins, 2020; Giray, 2021). This points out that the researcher needs to assess Junior High School teachers' work values in the four districts of Malungon.

Thus, this paper aimed to determine the work values of Junior High Teachers as a basis of the division, predominantly the Division of Sarangani, Municipality of Malungon, to design appropriate programs and policies related to teachers' working values. Knowledge of the teachers' work values brings light to the administrators and policymakers to create programs and activities related to the enhancement of working values, which is vital in developing teachers' teaching effectiveness needed to achieve the desired mission, vision, and goals set by the Department of Education.

Research Objective

1. What is the work values inventory of Junior High Teachers of Malungon Districts?
2. What intervention program could be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Work Adjustment by Dawis & Lofquist (1964) was the basis of this study; work is an interaction between a person and a work environment in which each has requirements of the other. There are specific tasks in a particular work environment, and an individual must perform these with all his best. This theory further explains that the person's abilities, particularly the skills, experience, attitudes, and values, correspond with the requirements of the role or the organization; the department anticipates that if an individual is doing his job well, his performance at work is outstanding.

Subsequently, the Personality Types Theory by Holland (1997) supported the abovementioned notion, emphasizing personalities and work environments. He believed that an individual chooses work based on his personality type. He characterized six ideal personality types such as realistic, investigative, artistic, social, enterprising, and conventional. This idea pointed out that people look for work environments that permit them to freely express their views, skills, interests, attitudes, and values and take on exciting problems and agreeable and satisfying roles. If a person feels this in his work setting, he is more likely to perform an admirable performance.

In addition, the Trait and Factor Theory developed by Parson (1909) showed resemblance with Holland's Personality Types Theory which lies on the premise that a person's personality traits are or are not a good fit for a factor of a particular workplace. For example, a person with high sociability would fit well with a job that requires interpersonal relationships but would not match well with a job of isolation.

In connection with the mentioned theories, the Vocational Development Theory of Super (1990) supported the ideas that work environments contribute to an individual's satisfaction with jobs. He stated that individuals know and understand themselves first when making a career choice. He also agreed that people seek career satisfaction through work roles in which they can fully express themselves and further enhance and develop their self-understanding. This claim may also result in an individual deciding to make career changes or remain in the career.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 presented the conceptual framework of the study. It showed the comprehensive process flow of how the study was carried out. The first section indicated the variable that causes the problem which is the work values of Junior High School Teachers. Through the use of survey questionnaire, systematic methods of data gathering procedures, statistical treatment and analysis of data, accurate findings were made which resulted to the formulation of an intervention program

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Significance of the study

The results of this study were beneficial because it primarily aimed to determine the Work values of Junior High School teachers in all districts of Malungon. The Department of Education (DepEd) may use the study's results to design programs and policies that would help address the existing problems of teachers' work values as one of the factors in improving their teaching performance. The strengths and weaknesses of the teachers would be identified and serve as the school's baseline to improve its management and operation, thus providing teachers with proper training focusing on personal and professional growth. Furthermore, this could also serve as the basis for reviewing the existing motivational policies and practices that would help enhance the teachers' work values.

Additionally, the researcher found this study very vital to the teachers because, as a catalyst of change and a person behind educational success and development, they should manifest positive working values to achieve the department's desired mission, vision, and goals. The study's results would also be an avenue for them to reflect on their self and performance; thus, conducting yearly self-evaluation when necessary.

Moreover, the data gathered could inform the parents about how teachers work hard to provide their children with better education. Finally, the results would benefit the researcher because these give additional references. Moreover, future researchers may utilize the study's findings to investigate the related variables further.

Definition of Terms

To better understand this study, the researcher defined significant variables operationally.

Work Values. It refers to how the Junior High School Teachers of Malungon Districts view his work and give importance to it. It also refers to the respondents' existing values in their jobs that may or may not affect their performance as teachers. The researcher used the Work Values Inventory to measure the work values of Junior High School Teachers.

Work Values Inventory. It refers to the instrument used by the researcher to know the work values of Junior High School Teachers in the Municipality of Malungon. The instruments contained forty-five statements about values people consider necessary in their work. The questionnaire allows the participant to choose one of the scales based on its importance. This instrument is a standardized psychological test from Donald E. Super (1970).

Junior High School Teachers. It refers to the respondents of this study subjected to the Work Values Inventory. They have regular-permanent items as Junior High School teachers and are presently teaching in either integrated school or secondary in the four districts of Malungon.

2. METHOD

This study utilized a descriptive research design, specifically the cross-sectional survey. A cross-sectional survey research design was the most suited design to utilize since the study aimed to determine the work values of Junior High School Teachers of Malungon Districts. A cross-sectional survey research design involved viewing respondents who vary on one main characteristic at a particular time. The respondents who were alike on other characteristics but altered on a simple feature of concern were the subject of data gathering, which takes place simultaneously (Bowden, 2011; Creswell, 2014; Wang & Cheng, 2020).

The setting of the study was the Municipality of Malungon. Malungon is a first-class municipality in the province of Sarangani. It is in the northeastern part of Sarangani province. It is Sarangani's gateway to the Davao Region, bordering General Santos City and the province of Davao del Sur.

The study's respondents were the 187 Junior High School teachers of the four districts of the Municipality of Malungon, taken from the total population of 349. The data source was from the Enhanced Basic Education Information System (EBEIS) of the Planning Office, Division of Sarangani.

The researcher identified the number of respondents in the study using Slovin Formula.

Moreover, the researcher used a simple random sampling technique through the use of draw lots. It was a sampling design wherein the group of respondents taken from a population chosen entirely by chance, and each respondent had an equal chance to be included in the sample (Hiram, 2013).

3. RESULT

Studies and literature have shown that work values are one of the predictors of good teaching performance. Positive work values are more likely to result in good teaching performance, and negative work values deteriorate teachers' performance (McKay, 2018; Pryce, 2014; Giray, 2021).

The data showed that the Work Values Inventory of Junior High School Teachers of East Malungon Districts were consistently high in achievement (13.81).

Table 1: Work Values Inventory of Junior High School Teachers of Malungon Districts

Work Values	East Malungon		North Malungon		South Malungon		West Malungon	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Achievement	13.81	Very Important	14.75	Very Important	14.26	Very Important	14.02	Very Important
Surroundings	13.38	Very Important	14.01	Very Important	14.06	Very Important	13.63	Very Important
Security	13.96	Very Important	13.78	Very Important	13.64	Very Important	13.69	Very Important
Prestige	12.18	Very Important	12.74	Very Important	12.99	Very Important	11.66	Very Important
Economic Return	13.09	Very Important	12.68	Very Important	13.44	Very Important	12.58	Very Important
Creativity	13.43	Very Important	14.30	Very Important	14.08	Very Important	13.24	Very Important
Management	9.35	Moderately Important	13.08	Very Important	8.89	Moderately Important	8.44	Moderately Important
Aesthetic	12.53	Very Important	9.02	Moderately Important	12.76	Very Important	12.55	Very Important
Variety	12.85	Very Important	12.84	Very Important	12.72	Very Important	12.15	Very Important
Intellectual Stimulation	12.82	Very Important	13.2	Very Important	13.02	Very Important	13.03	Very Important
Supervisory Relationships	13.66	Very Important	13.96	Very Important	14.11	Very Important	13.87	Very Important
Associates	13.05	Very Important	13.37	Very Important	13.21	Very Important	12.58	Very Important
Altruism	13.99	Very Important	14.34	Very Important	14.05	Very Important	14.24	Very Important
Way of Life	13.92	Very Important	13.59	Very Important	13.52	Very Important	13.10	Very Important
Independence	12.67	Very Important	12.42	Very Important	12.76	Very Important	12.31	Very Important

Surroundings (13.38), Security (13.96), Economic Return (13.09), Creativity

(13.43), Aesthetic (12.53), Variety (12.85), Intellectual Stimulation (12.82),

Supervisory relationship (13.66), Associates (13.05), Altruism (13.99), Way of Life (13.92) and independence (12.97) which fell within the same descriptions as "Very Important." On the other hand, Management was consistently low in this district with a mean of 9.35, which fell under the description of "moderately important."

While, the work values inventory of Junior High School Teachers of North Malungon was consistently high in all indicators of work values except for aesthetic, with the mean of 9.02, which fell under the description of "moderately important." This result implied that these teachers gave moderate importance to work which permitted them to develop artistic abilities and make and develop attractive outputs. However, achievement (14.75), surrounding (14.01), Security (13.96), Prestige (12.74), Economic return (12.68), creativity (14.30), Management (13.08), Variety (12.84), Intellectual stimulation (13.2), Supervisory relationship (13.96), Associates (13.37), Altruism (13.34), way of life (13.59) and independence (12.42) were ranked by the teachers of North Malungon as very important work values.

On the other hand, the work values inventory of Junior High School Teachers of South Malungon consistently fell within the same level of weighted mean with the interpretation of "Very important" such as achievement (14.26), surrounding (14.06), Security (13.64), Prestige (12.99), Economic return (13.44), creativity (14.08), Aesthetic (12.76), Variety (12.72), Intellectual stimulation (13.02), Supervisory relationship (14.11), Associates (13.21), Altruism (14.05), way of life (13.52) and independence (12.76). On the contrary, management work values were also low in these groups of teachers, with a mean of 8.89 and a "moderately important" description.

On the contrary, work values such as achievement (14.02), surroundings (13.63), Security (13.69), Economic return (12.58), Creativity (13.24), Aesthetic (12.55), Intellectual Stimulation (13.03), Supervisory Relationships (13.87), Associates (12.58), Altruism (14.24), and Way of life (13.10) were considered by the Junior High School Teachers of West Malungon Districts as very important work values. These teachers rated Prestige, Variety, and independence, with the mean of 11.66, 12.15, and 12.31 as "important" work values. While Management with a mean of 8.44 considered a "moderately important" work value.

4. DISCUSSION

The study's findings showed that each district's work values inventory was consistently high in all work values, with the mean falling on the interpretation level as "very important" work values. This result meant Junior High School teachers were more engaged in positive, fulfilling, and rewarding jobs. Gallie (2019) stated that if teachers were engaged at work, they were willing to carry out their roles and jobs as teachers and were still willing to accept extra work. Moreover, it is expected for Junior High School teachers to have work values such as discipline, creativity, orderliness, patience, decisiveness, and achievement.

Results also showed that Junior High School teachers of East Malungon, South Malungon, and West Malungon considered management a moderately important work value. This result significantly meant that these teachers gave moderate importance to work which permit them to plan and layout work for others. In the study by Basinska & Daderman (2019), work values such as management are considered extrinsic values related to instrumental aspects of work and provide external rewards or satisfaction such as salary, prestige, or job security.

Furthermore, Evangelista (2019) cited that teachers failed to recognize that the management work value must be a priority because, as teachers, they were also classroom managers. Teachers who take the lead in planning and have high management values are more likely to be efficient and effective teachers because they make the teaching and learning process attainable and provide precise and clear directions to students.

Moreover, Herman, Reinke, Dong & Bradshaw (2020) viewed teachers' good management values improve students' behavior outcomes. Teachers in the training condition improved management practices and improved learners' pro-social behavior and self-regulation. Moreover, finding ways to improve the management skills of teachers should be a priority for policymakers, for it holds promise for increasing student achievement on a large scale.

On the other hand, the Junior High School Teachers of North Malungon Districts considered aesthetics moderately important work value with a mean score of 9.02. This result pointedly meant that these teachers gave moderate importance to work which permit them to develop artistic abilities and make and develop attractive outputs. As viewed by Cherry (2019), intrinsic values are work values that focus on work outcomes that are related to psychological rewards such as recognition, the opportunity for growth, and thriving.

Additionally, Shih (2020) regarded the idea that people have innate aesthetic talent and that education must cultivate it through daily life and interaction with others. It is advised for teachers, as the backbone of the educational system, to practice aesthetic values at school so they can infuse them into their learners. Furthermore, if teachers practice aesthetic work values, he/she can expand learners' aesthetic experiences and enhance their aesthetic literacy.

Subsequently, the study of Abdullah, Ling & Hassan (2018) concluded that teachers must possess a positive attitude and work value towards progress as the front liner of the nation's education system. Teachers should have a strong personality and credibility in helping to realize the desired vision, mission, and goals the Department of Education sets. Thus, various efforts such as enhancing teachers' work values need to craft.

Additionally, Giray (2021) supported this study, which made significant recommendations that participating in activities that hone teachers' work-related values must be sustained like attending seminars, self-reflection, mentoring, and seeking feedback from colleagues. Similarly, Yariv (2011) cited that combating teachers' professional and personal hardships

requires a concerted multi-level systematic and ongoing program. Such intervention may handle along with five consecutive steps; identify and agree upon the problem, establish the reasons for underperformance, decide and agree on the action required, resource this action to train and monitor performance, and provide feedback.

In addition, the results of this study supported the Theory of Work Adjustment by Dawis and Lofquist (1984), which states that there are specific tasks to perform in a particular work environment, and an individual needs to perform them with all his best. The theory further explains that the person's abilities, particularly the skills, experience, attitudes, and values, correspond with the requirements of the role or the organization; the department anticipates that if an individual is doing his job well, his performance at work is outstanding.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the work values of Junior High School Teachers of Malungon Districts were consistently high in achievement, surroundings, security, prestige, economic return, creativity, variety, intellectual stimulation, supervisory relationships, altruism, way of life and independence. Management work values were considered by Junior High School Teachers of West, East, and South Malungon Districts as moderately important work values, while aesthetics was rated by Junior High School Teachers of North Malungon as moderately important work values. Moreover, the proposed intervention program per district to enhance teachers' work values in management and aesthetics should be imposed. The results supported the Theory of Work Adjustment by Dawis and Lofquist (1984), which suggested that a person must perform his jobs with all his best and that his experiences, abilities, skills, and values correspond with the requirements set by the organizations/department.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Given the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher strongly suggests that administrators must continue to encourage the Junior High School Teachers to sustain their work values for the betterment of the school and the learners. They may design works, activities, programs, and pieces of training that encourage teachers to practice and enhance their work values, especially those they rated moderately important. Likewise, the District Supervisors should design and implement an intervention program to address the teachers' least common work values per district, or they may also adopt the intervention program designed by the researcher found in this study. Furthermore, as the backbones of the department, teachers should sustain their work values in realizing the Department of Education's mission, vision, and goals. Finally, future researchers may utilize the study's findings to investigate the related variables further.

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